

Statistical analysis plan

Emulation of Cardiovascular Outcomes in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes: A Comparative Study of Sitagliptin versus Thiazolidinedione/Sulfonylurea Using Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) Data - Insights from the TECOS Trial

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1. Overview of [TECOS](#) trial:

The primary objective of the TECOS trial was to assess the cardiovascular safety of Sitagliptin, a dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitor, in patients with type 2 diabetes and established cardiovascular disease. The TECOS trial was a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled study. Participants were randomly assigned to receive either sitagliptin or a placebo, in addition to their usual diabetes care. Usual care could include other glucose-lowering therapies as determined by their healthcare providers. The study included a large sample size of 14,671 participants and had a median follow-up period of approximately 3 years. Participants included in the TECOS trial were adults with type 2 diabetes and a history of cardiovascular disease. This population was selected to specifically evaluate the cardiovascular safety of sitagliptin in individuals at high risk for cardiovascular events due to their existing medical conditions[1].

Primary Endpoint:

The primary endpoint of the TECOS trial was a composite of major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE), which included cardiovascular death, nonfatal myocardial infarction, nonfatal stroke, and hospitalisation for unstable angina. This endpoint was chosen to comprehensively capture the most significant cardiovascular outcomes relevant to the study population.

Secondary Endpoints:

Secondary endpoints included all-cause mortality, hospitalisation for heart failure, and the individual components of the primary endpoint. These endpoints were analysed to provide additional insights into the effects of sitagliptin on various cardiovascular outcomes and overall mortality.

Key Findings:

The TECOS trial found that sitagliptin did not increase the risk of major adverse cardiovascular events compared to placebo. Specifically, the primary composite endpoint occurred in 11.4% of the sitagliptin group versus 11.6% in the placebo group, indicating no significant difference. Additionally, there was no significant difference in the rate of hospitalisation for heart failure between the sitagliptin and placebo groups. Sitagliptin was also found to provide effective glycaemic control without an increased risk of hypoglycaemia.

2. Trial Emulation Study Design

2.1 Study population

In England, the NHS provides health care, free at the point of administration. We will use data from the Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) to evaluate the cardiovascular disease outcomes of sitagliptin in individuals with type 2 diabetes with established cardiovascular disease. The CPRD was launched in 2012 by the UK Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) and the Department of Health's National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR). It was previously known as the Value Added Medical Products (VAMP) when established in 1987 followed by the General Practice Research Database (GPRD) from 1993, which were both smaller datasets. The CPRD dataset is now considered to be one of the largest sources of longitudinal primary care data in the world, comprised of anonymised electronic health record data collected every month by general practices in the UK. Patient information collected include data on demographics, clinical tests, diagnoses and

treatments, referrals, behavioural factors and immunisations. Linked data from secondary care or other health-related data are also available in CPRD such as hospitalisation data (from Hospital Episode Statistics datasets), mortality data (from Office for National Statistics datasets) and deprivation data (from Index of Multiple Deprivation and Townsend scores datasets) [2].

2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

To ensure the target trial and the emulated trial using observational data are comparable, we need to establish a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria based on clinical expertise. This step is crucial for defining a consistent and relevant participant population, which minimises biases and enhances the validity of the comparisons.

Table 1- Proposed Trial Emulation inclusion criteria using CPRD data

<i>Trial*</i>	<i>Emulation</i>
Patients with T2DM has not previously required insulin other than for a short term, reversible illness (less than three consecutive months of insulin use), or during pregnancy.	Patients \geq 50 years are considered to have type 2 diabetes if treated with an Sitagliptin rather than insulin and without prior use of insulin.
Age \geq 50 yrs.	Age \geq 50 years at the treatment of interest initiation
Patient is receiving metformin, pioglitazone, or a sulfonylurea as monotherapy or any dual combination of metformin, pioglitazone, or a sulfonylurea continuously for at least 3 months without dose alterations, and has an HbA1c of \geq 6.5% and \leq 8.0% (HbA1c must be documented within 3 months prior to study enrolment).	HbA1c 48-64 mmol/mol at the latest measurement before baseline, max 1 year before. This excludes all those without an HbA1c measurement.
Patient is \geq 50 years of age with pre-existing vascular disease, defined as having any one of the following:	Prevalent disease is defined by any occurrence, looking 10 years back from baseline.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> History of a major clinical manifestation of coronary artery disease (i.e., myocardial infarction, surgical or percutaneous [balloon and/or stent] coronary revascularization procedure, or coronary angiography showing at least one stenosis \geq 50% in a major epicardial artery or branch vessel); 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ischemic cerebrovascular disease, including: History of ischemic stroke and History of carotid arterial disease as documented by \geq 50 % stenosis documented by carotid ultrasound, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), or angiography, with or without symptoms of neurologic deficit. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Atherosclerotic peripheral arterial disease, as documented by objective evidence such as amputation due to vascular disease, current symptoms of intermittent claudication confirmed by an ankle-brachial pressure index or toe brachial pressure index less than 0.9 or history of surgical or percutaneous revascularization procedure. 	

*Complete list of inclusion criteria based on trial appendix

Table 2 – Trial Emulation exclusion criteria using CPRD

<i>Trial*</i>	<i>Emulation</i>
Patient has a history of type 1 diabetes mellitus, a history of ketoacidosis, or is currently taking insulin	
Patient has taken an approved or investigational DPP-4 inhibitor agent, GLP-1 analogues, or a thiazolidinedione other than pioglitazone within the past 3 months.	Evaluated 90 days prior to baseline
Patient has cirrhosis of the liver, as assessed by medical history	
Patient has a planned or anticipated revascularization procedure	
Pregnancy	
Patient has medical history that indicates a life expectancy of < 2 years or might limit the individual's ability to take trial treatments for the duration of the study	
Patient has an estimated GFR of < 30 mL/min/1.73 m ²	
Patient has a known allergy or intolerance to sitagliptin	

*Complete list of exclusion criteria based on trial appendix

Study duration and follow up:

The index date (time zero) is defined as the first instance when a patient redeems a prescription for one of the pharmacotherapies of interest and meets the inclusion and exclusion criteria within the specified time period. Follow up measurements if available, refer to measurements closest to the middle of the interval.

Treatment of interest

In the original trial, patients were randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to receive either sitagliptin at a dose of 100 mg daily (or 50 mg daily if the baseline eGFR was ≥ 30 and < 50 ml per minute per 1.73 m^2) or matching placebo. For the emulated trial using observational data, we will employ second-line glucose-lowering therapies from the thiazolidinedione drug class and sulfonylurea class as the comparator arm.

The aim of trial emulation is to primarily “compare taking sitagliptin continuously during the follow-up, unless otherwise clinically indicated with continuous treatment with thiazolidinedione/ or sulfonylurea class unless otherwise clinically indicated”. Our approach involves using a discrete time scale with intervals of six months. Patients will be considered "on treatment" within a specific time interval if they redeemed at least one prescription during that interval. This method allows us to simulate real-world treatment scenarios and assess comparative effectiveness over time between these two classes of medications.

Outcome(s):

Table 3- primary and secondary outcomes in TECOS trial and Emulation

<i>Trial</i>	<i>Emulation</i>
Primary endpoint	
first confirmed event of cardiovascular death, nonfatal myocardial infarction, nonfatal stroke, or hospitalisation for unstable angina.	CVD death, Stroke, MI, unstable angina
Secondary endpoint	
The secondary composite cardiovascular outcome was the first confirmed event of cardiovascular death, nonfatal myocardial infarction, or nonfatal stroke.	CVD death, MI, or Stroke
Occurrence of the individual components of the primary composite cardiovascular outcome, fatal and nonfatal myocardial infarction, fatal and nonfatal stroke, death from any cause, and hospitalisation for heart failure.	

Potential confounders:

Pre-treatment and baseline variable	Time-varying variables
Age (continuous)	Adding hypoglycaemic treatment (excluding drugs affecting the incretin pathway)
Sex (male, female or unspecified)	Adding GLP-1
Index of multiple deprivation (calculated from each individuals postcode)	Incident heart failure
Duration of diabetes (categorised as 0-5, 5-10, >10 years)	Incident peripheral artery disease
HbA1c (continuous), recorded a maximum of 1 year before start of treatment	Incident renal disease
Cholesterol (continuous), recorded a maximum of 1 year before start of treatment	Incident diabetic eye disease
Blood pressure (continuous), recorded a maximum of 1 year before start of treatment	Incident chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
Glomerular filtration rate based on creatinine (eGFR), recorded a maximum of 1 year before start of treatment	Incident hypertension
Concomitant glucose lowering treatment	Incident atrial fibrillation
History of atrial fibrillation	HbA1c (continuous)
History of myocardial infarction	
History of heart failure	

History of stroke	
History of peripheral artery disease	
History of renal disease	
History of diabetic eye disease	
History of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	
History of hypertension	
Therapy with:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Aldosterone receptor antagonists 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Beta-blockers 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors/angiotensin receptor-2 blockers 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Loop diuretics 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Calcium channel blockers 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Thiazide diuretics 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Acetylsalicylic acid (aspirin) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Statins 	

Concomitant Glucose-Lowering Treatment, included as a baseline covariate by examining the treatment 180 days before baseline and as a time-varying confounder if initiated after baseline.

3. Data preparation:

We will explore the distribution of all continuous variables using relevant measures and graphs, such as measures of central tendency and variation, box plots, histograms, and Q-Q plots, to identify outliers. Any outliers found will be checked to determine if they are clinically plausible or if they are due to measurement error.

To address missing data, we will check the mechanism of missingness using formal tests like Little's MCAR test and graphical methods, such as heatmap plots. For data imputation, we will use random forest -based methods i.e. Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations Random Forest (MICE RF)[14],). Studies have shown that this method is suitable for complex epidemiological studies and can produce unbiased estimates of (log) hazard ratios. Parameter estimates are less biased using random forest MICE, and confidence interval coverage is improved [15].

4. Analysis

4.1 Target parameter of interest

Risk difference/ratio between taking sitagliptin for 1-3 years (unless otherwise clinically indicated), compared to taking treatment within thiazolidinedione/ or sulfonylurea class for 1-3 years (unless otherwise clinically indicated).

4.2 Descriptive analysis

Initially, we will calculate summary statistics for both continuous and categorical variables. Continuous variables will be described using measures of central tendency such as mean and median, and measures of dispersion like standard deviation and interquartile range. Categorical variables will be summarised with frequencies and percentages.

Baseline characteristics will be compared between treatment groups using appropriate statistical tests to assess the balance before treatment initiation. Additionally, we will provide a detailed summary of the use of sitagliptin and thiazolidinedione/ or sulfonylurea, both as initial and time-varying treatments, and the incidence of primary and secondary outcomes across treatment groups. For time-varying variables, incidence rates over time will be calculated, and Kaplan-Meier curves will visualise time-to-event data for key outcomes. After performing multiple imputations, we will compare the distribution of imputed data with the original data to ensure that imputation has not introduced bias. These descriptive analyses will provide a solid foundation for the subsequent inferential analyses, ensuring that any findings are based on a thorough understanding of the data.

To capture changes in HbA1c levels over time, we will use longitudinal graphs. These graphs will display the trends in HbA1c for both medication groups, highlighting how glycaemic control evolves during the study period. By plotting individual patient trajectories as well as group averages, we can observe the overall effectiveness and variability of each treatment. Additionally, these graphs will help identify any significant shifts in HbA1c levels that may correspond with treatment adjustments or discontinuations.

Furthermore, we will analyse prescription patterns and treatment adherence using longitudinal data. Graphs will show the frequency of treatment dropouts and switches, providing insights into patient adherence and the sustainability of each treatment strategy. These visualisations will enable us to identify common reasons for discontinuation and assess whether patients who switch treatments exhibit different clinical outcomes compared to those who remain on their initial medication.

4.3 Longitudinal Targeted Maximum Likelihood Estimation (LTMLE)

We will employ a discrete time scale with periods of six months ($t=0, 6, 12, \dots, 36$) to estimate the target parameters using a longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimator (LTMLE). LTMLE is a robust statistical method that accounts for time-varying covariates and treatments, providing accurate and unbiased causal effect estimates [3, 4].

Our data will be structured into 6-month intervals, creating a longitudinal dataset where each participant has multiple records corresponding to each 6-month period. Each record will include both time-varying covariates (e.g., HbA1c levels, incident health conditions, concomitant medications) and treatment status for that interval. Baseline covariates such as age, sex, and initial health conditions will be included as static variables.

LTMLE updates an initial sequential regression estimator using inverse probability weighting, accounting for the propensity of treatment and the probability of not being censored using Super Learner approach. SL is an ensemble method that allows researchers to combine several different prediction algorithms into one where the candidate algorithms can be quite different. It uses K-fold cross-validation to build the optimally weighted combination of predictions from a library of candidate machine learning algorithms [5, 6]. The estimation procedure involves several key steps:

Model Specification:

Define models for the treatment mechanism (the probability of receiving Sitagliptin versus taking treatment within thiazolidinedione/ or sulfonylurea class given past covariates and treatment history) and the outcome mechanism (the probability of the outcome given past covariates and treatment history).

Initial Estimates:

Obtain initial estimates of the outcome and treatment probabilities using these models. All nuisance parameter regression models necessary for the initial estimator and for the targeting step will be adjusted for additive effects of all covariates updated to the current time interval, ensuring the causal time order of the variables is maintained.

Targeted Update:

Apply a targeting step to adjust the initial estimates using inverse probability weights. Specifically, we will regress the outcome, treatment, and censoring variables defined in the calendar time interval ($t, t+6$ months) on the most recent values of the time-dependent covariates at time t and the entire history of the treatment variables up to time t .

Penalised Ridge Regression:

Fit all nuisance parameter models using penalised ridge regression, selecting penalty parameters to under smooth the regression fits, which helps in reducing the bias in the estimates.

Iterative Process:

The targeting step is iterated until the estimates converge, ensuring the final estimates are consistent with the observed data and the specified causal model.

Reporting and Interpretation:

The primary analysis will focus on estimating the causal effect of continuous treatment with Sitagliptin versus taking treatment within thiazolidinedione/ or sulfonylurea class on the primary and secondary outcomes over the study period. We will report the longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimates (LTMLE) with 95% confidence intervals. These estimates will provide robust and interpretable causal insights into the comparative effectiveness of Sitagliptin versus thiazolidinedione/ or sulfonylurea in real-world clinical practice.

By employing LTMLE, we address the complexities of time-varying treatments and covariates, ensuring that our analysis correctly models the dynamic nature of treatment effects and confounding factors over time. This approach will yield reliable and nuanced insights into the long-term impacts of these diabetes treatments.

4.4 Subgroup and sensitivity analysis

we will stratify our analysis of the primary and secondary outcomes across several key demographic and clinical subgroups. These subgroups include sex, age group, ethnicity, baseline HbA1c levels, duration of diabetes, and history of a previous cardiovascular event. By examining treatment effects within these subpopulations, we aim to identify potential variations in treatment response and assess the generalisability of our findings across diverse patient profiles.

As part of our sensitivity analysis, we will implement a grace period of 30 days by shifting the index date to day 30 after treatment initiation. This adjustment allows for a more flexible definition of treatment exposure, accounting for potential delays in treatment response or adherence variations during

the initial phase of therapy. Following the adjustment, we will repeat our main analysis, including the estimation of primary and secondary outcomes, within this modified timeframe [7].

By conducting sensitivity analyses, we can evaluate the robustness of our primary findings and assess the potential impact of methodological variations on our results. The inclusion of a grace period addresses potential misclassification of treatment exposure and ensures that our estimates remain valid under alternative modelling assumptions. Overall, these sensitivity analyses enhance the reliability and validity of our study findings, providing a comprehensive evaluation of the treatment effects observed in our primary analysis.

Appendix:

Table S1- Glucose-lowering prescriptions available in CPRD

Medication	ATC code
Glucose-lowering prescriptions	
DDP-4 inhibitors	Z79.84
GLP-1 receptor agonists	Z79.84
Glucosidase inhibitors	Z79.84
Insulin	Z79.84
Meglitinides	Z79.84
Metformin	Z79.84
SGLT2 inhibitors	Z79.84
Sulfonylureas	Z79.84
Thiazolidinediones	Z79.84
Blood pressure lowering prescriptions	Z79.51 Z79.52 Z79.899 Z79.899 Z79.899
Aldosterone receptor antagonists	Z79.899
Beta-blockers	Z79.51
Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors/angiotensin receptor-2 blockers	Z79.52
Loop diuretics	Z79.899
Calcium channel blockers,	Z79.899
Thiazide	Z79.899
Cholesterol-lowering prescriptions	Z79.02
Statins	Z79.02

Table S2- Secondary care data and mortality data available through linkage of CPRD

Medical Condition	ICD codes
Heart failure	I50.1, I50.20-23, I50.30-33, I50.40-43, I50.9
Myocardial infarction	I121.0-9, I122.0-9
Stroke	I61.0-9, I63.0-9, I166, I169
Peripheral artery disease	I170.20-29
Renal disease	N18.3-5, E10.2, E11.2
Diabetic eye disease	E11.319, 321. 331, 341, 351, E11.321, 3211, 331, 3311, 341, 3411, 351, 3511, E11.39
Atrial Fibrillation	I48.0, 148.1, 148.11, I48.11, I48.19, I482, 21, 3, 4, 91, 92, I44.91, 92,
Hypertension	I10, I11, I11.0, 11.9
Cancer	C00-C14, C15-26, C30-39, C40-41, C43-58, C60-97
Liver disease	K70-77
Endocrine disorder except type 2 diabetes	E00-07, E15-16, E20-35
Alcohol or drug abuse	F10-19
Chronic Obstructive pulmonary disease	J40, J43, J44
Unstable Angina	I20.0-9, I24
Bariatric surgery	0DBM0ZZ
Revascularization	02703ZZ 02713ZZ, 02723ZZ 02733ZZ 02763ZZ 02773ZZ 02783ZZ 02793ZZ 02793ZZ
Mortality	R99
All-cause mortality	R99
Cardiovascular mortality	

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